

Novatians

also known as “Novatian schism, Novatianism”

By Lampros Alexopoulos, University of Thessaloniki

Entry tags: Christian Traditions, Early Christianity, Heresy, Religious Group, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Orthodoxy

One of the oldest schisms in the Early Church is the Novatian schism. After the persecution of Decius (249-250) arose a disagreement within the Church of Rome about the way to accept the Christians who denied their Christian faith, because of the persecutions and the pressure to worship pagan idols. The result of this disagreement was the Novatian schism (251). Novatian (or Novatus) was a scholar (Stoic philosopher before his conversion to Christianity), who became a priest and a noted theologian and prolific writer. He was the first Roman theologian who used the Latin language. After the death of the Bishop of Rome Fabianus (236-250), who was killed in prison, the administration of the local Church was taken over by elders and deacons, with Novatian as their head. With the end of the persecutions of Decius the elders faced the question of the admission to the Church of those who had lapsed and wished to return to the Christian faith, as well as the issue of their penance. They thus adopted the so-called lifelong penance, meaning that the lapsed would be accepted to the Church on their deathbed. In March 251, with the emperor Decius's death, the persecution began to subside and the Roman community seized the opportunity to nominate a successor to Fabian. Although Novatian was an eminent theologian in Rome and had a hand in running the Church after the death of Fabian, the moderate Roman aristocrat Cornelius (251-253) was elected. Cornelius adopted a more lenient attitude towards those who did not sacrifice to idols, but refused Christianity in a written declaration. The lapsed could be restored to communion after varying forms of repentance, demonstrated by a period of penance. Those who supported a more rigorous position, however, had Novatian consecrated as bishop and refused to recognize Cornelius as Bishop of Rome. In 251, Cornelius assembled a council of sixty bishops in Rome to acknowledge him as the rightful pope and excommunicated Novatian, as well as all of his followers, while the council settled also the question of the lapsed. While Novatian had refused redemption to the those who had renounced their Christianity under persecution but later wanted to return to the Church, his followers extended the doctrine to include all “mortal sins”, such as idolatry, murder, and adultery, or fornication. Many of them forbade second marriage as well. The repentance of these groups was lifelong in the broadest sense, that is, until the Second Coming, when the Lord Himself would judge them. Novatians considered the baptism of the clergy under the Bishop Cornelius invalid, so they and baptized those who joined their sect. Intolerant and authoritarian himself, Novatian forced his followers to swear that they would not follow Cornelius of Rome. Novatian died in 258, probably during Valerian's persecutions. After his death, Novatianist churches continued to thrive side by side with the orthodox churches up to the fifth century in the West and up to the eighth century in the East, particularly in Asia Minor. In the West, Novatianist communities with their own bishops spread from Rome and Africa as far as Spain. Those who allied themselves with his doctrines were called Novatianists, but they called themselves “Catharoi” or “Purists” (not to be confused with the later Cathars) to reflect their desire not to be identified with what they regarded as the lax and tolerant practices of a corrupt ecclesiastical power. They always had a successor of Novatian at Rome. Some Novatians blended with the Montanists and, mostly in the East, many of the cities of Phrygia (former stronghold of the Montanists) had Novatianist bishops. The last of their communities survived till the end of the seventh century.

Date Range: 250 CE - 258 CE

Region: Rome, Italy

Region tags: Europe, Southeastern Europe, Southern Europe, Italy, Rome

The Church of Rome was the playground for the Novatian schism.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Papandrea, James L., *Novatian of Rome: On the Trinity, Letters to Cyprian of Carthage, Ethical Treatises*, Translation with Introduction, Turnhout: Brepols, 2015.
- Source 2: Papandrea, JL, *The Trinitarian Theology of Novatian of Rome: A Study in Third-Century Orthodoxy*, Lewiston, NJ, 2008.
- Source 3: Vogt, HJ, *Coetus Sanctorum. Der Kirchenbegriff des Novatian und die Geschichte seiner Sonderkirche*, Bonn, 1968.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20190403211934/http://www.newadvent.org/cathen/11138a.htm>
- Source 1 Description: Novatian and Novatianism
- Source 2 URL: http://www.documentacatholicaomnia.eu/30_10_0251-0258-_Novatianus.html
- Source 2 Description: Novatian Works
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.ccel.org/ccel/wace/bioidict.html?term=Novatianus%20and%20Novatianism>
- Source 3 Description: Novatianus and Novatianism, Dictionary of Christian Biography

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://bvk.unifr.ch/de/works/cpl-77/versions/a-treatise-against-the-heretic-novatian-by-an-anonymous-bishop/divisions/2>
 - Source 1 Description: "Contra Novatianos": A Treatise Against the Heretic Novatian by an Anonymous Bishop
 - Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/antenicenefathe10menzgoog>
 - Source 2 Description: *The Ante-Nicene Fathers: the writings of the Fathers down to A.D. 325. Vol 1.*
 - Source 3 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/34061.htm>
 - Source 3 Description: Ambrose of Milan, *Concerning Repentance (Book I)*
- Notes: Novatian, *On the Jewish Meats* (<https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/0512.htm>)

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: The Novatians used the Bible, like all Christians. In fact, Novatian was a keen theologian and is considered one of the pioneers of Latin Theology. In his work "De Trinitate" he quotes extensively from the Bible (both the Old and the New Testament), providing extensive biblical proofs about the Holy Trinity, the divinity of Christ and of the Holy Spirit.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: In the East, and particularly at the region of Phrygia, many of the cities that have been stronghold of the Montanists had Novatian bishops. It has further been suggested that several followers of Novatian blended with Montanist adherents.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Re-baptism.

Notes: The Novatians would rebaptize people who came from the Catholic Church, since they believed they were sinners.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is iconography present:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Not exactly. Before Novatian's schism, he had strongly denied that the Church had the right to condone the apostasy of the lapsed even at the moment of death. This view was contradictory to his previous views, when he considered the desire for reconciliation of the lapsed as lawful, agreeing to the reconciliation of those in danger of death who had not yet done full penance. This is why Novatian was accused by Cyprian for tolerating defrauders and adulterers in his Church, but at the same time he unmercifully rejected the lapsed.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: In the East, and particularly at the region of Phrygia, many of the cities that have been stronghold of the Montanists had Novatian bishops. It has further been suggested that several followers of Novatian blended with Montanist adherents.

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↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

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↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

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– Yes

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Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

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Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Notes: Only implicitly and vaguely. Novatian states, in the context of praising purity, that the flesh forever tends downwards and can carry purity along with it, while the spirit must, as much as possible, restrain the flesh. One's frame of mind should be far removed from things of the flesh. In this sense, there is a spirit-body distinction, however this idea is not fully developed.

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that Novatians had a theory of a Messianic Church, heroic and in conflict with the world.

Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Field doesn't know

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Novatians held that the duties of a bishop included the imparting of the knowledge of those divine truths which were promulgated and expounded by the Lord Himself, so that believers might attain the promised kingdom of heaven, and instill hope of the attainment of eternal life.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: According to Novatian the daily life is laudable, therefore Christians should remain faithful to their profession of faith. He holds that the pleasure one gets from the spectacles is blameless because it is merely a means of mental relaxation. It is not permissible for faithful Christians to be present in theaters or the hippodrome and the other spectacles. On the contrary, the faithful Christians must shun such vain, such pernicious, such sacrilegious spectacles. It is imperative that their eyes and ears be guarded from them, as one soon gets accustomed to what he hears and more quickly still to what he sees. Since man's mind is of itself inclined to sin, what will become of it if it is faced with living models of vice. Hence, a faithful Christian should occupy himself with the Sacred Scriptures, where he will find spectacles that become his faith.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals within society

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Only implicitly, in an epistle, Novatian claims that God, although is compassionate, He also strictly demands the observance of His precepts. He invites guests to His wedding banquet, but those that who wear no wedding garment will be cast out by his hands and feet from the assembly of the saints. He also mentions that God has prepared heaven, but He has also prepared Tartarus; has prepared refreshment, but He has also prepared eternal punishment; has prepared inaccessible light, finally, but He has also prepared the desolate and eternal darkness of perpetual night.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

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Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - No
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes

Notes: Novatians held that modesty strives to avoid anything that is beyond measure, improper, extravagant, artfully made-up, and meretriciously devised either to offend or to attract attention.

They even advocated that one should not look too inquisitively into the faces of strangers; that one's speech should be measured and the laughter contained, since laughter betrays an easygoing and dissipated spirit. Even virtuous contacts should be avoided.

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– No

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The evangelical virtue.

Notes: According to Novatian, the thought of attaining eternal rewards should likewise inflame

the mind to practice evangelical virtue. Furthermore, Novatian places the virtue of purity in greater relief, as the gift of God, and holds that there are three degrees of purity: virginity, continence, and faithfulness to the marriage bond.

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

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Are messianic beliefs present:

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Notes: It is believed that Novatians had a theory of a Messianic Church, heroic and in conflict with the world.

Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Field doesn't know

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: According to Novatian the daily life is laudable, therefore Christians should remain faithful to their profession of faith. He holds that the pleasure one gets from the spectacles is blameless because it is merely a means of mental relaxation. It is not permissible for faithful Christians to be present in theaters or the hippodrome and the other spectacles. On the contrary, the faithful Christians must shun such vain, such pernicious, such sacrilegious spectacles. It is imperative that their eyes and ears be guarded from them, as one soon gets accustomed to what he hears and more quickly still to what he sees. Since man's mind is of itself inclined to sin, what will become of it if it is faced with living models of vice. Hence, a faithful Christian should occupy himself with the Sacred Scriptures, where he will find spectacles that become his faith.

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↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The evangelical virtue.

Notes: According to Novatian, the thought of attaining eternal rewards should likewise inflame the mind to practice evangelical virtue. Furthermore, Novatian places the virtue of purity in greater relief, as the gift of God, and holds that there are three degrees of purity: virginity, continence, and faithfulness to the marriage bond.

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: However, Novatians believe that to maintain sexual purity of life from birth is a token of truly admirable virtue and to maintain oneself in the purity of an infant throughout the whole of one's life, even to old age, it is a greater blessing never to have known the seductive demands of the flesh. According to Novatian, virginity makes itself equal to the angels and it even outdoes the angels because it must struggle against flesh to gain mastery over a nature angels do not possess.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: Novatians forbade remarriage. According to Novatian, woman was brought forth from man that she can know no other except him; and woman is given back to man so that, when what had been taken out of him is restored to him, he may not seek for anything belonging to another.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Novatians forbade remarriage. According to Novatian, woman was brought forth from man that she can know no other except him; and woman is given back to man so that, when what had been taken out of him is restored to him, he may not seek for anything belonging to another.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Novatians held that it is virtuous to set down certain restrictions in marriage regarding continence.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Novatians held that it is virtuous to set down certain restrictions in marriage regarding continence.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no explicit mention in fasting. However, Novatians held that we should choose only the things that improve our soul and, although in the Gospel the use of foods is granted to us in every respect, one must realize that the use of these foods is given to us, however, with the law of frugality and moderation. In this sense, this kind of choice could be considered as a mode of fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Novatian wrote an epistle discussing the prohibitions that the Jewish Law enforced on certain types of food. According to Novatian, Divine benevolence has provided human needs with adequate kinds of foods to suit every age. Hearty flesh meat is proffered to men who must now cultivate the entire world and not merely take care of paradise. Since the cultivation of the land requires so much exertion, the human body had to be sustained with something more substantial. It is evident that all these foods enjoy again the blessings they received at their creation, now that the Law has ended, and that Christians must not return to the legal prohibition of foods commanded for certain reasons, and which evangelical liberty, setting Christians free from its bondage, has now discontinued. However, Novatian holds that Christians should not partake of what has been offered to idols. Although with regard to God's creation every food is clean, once it has been offered to demons, it is defiled for God, insofar as it is offered to idols. When this is taken as food, it nourishes the one who partakes of it for the devil, not for God, and makes him a table-companion of an idol, not of Christ.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Novatian's followers deliberately separated themselves and their communities from other Christian communities and called themselves "Catharoi" or "Purists" to reflect their desire not to be identified with what they regarded as the lax and tolerant practices of a corrupt ecclesiastical power.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: However, Novatians believe that to maintain sexual purity of life from birth is a token of truly admirable virtue and to maintain oneself in the purity of an infant throughout the whole of one's life, even to old age, it is a greater blessing never to have known the seductive demands of the flesh. According to Novatian, virginity makes itself equal to the angels and it even outdoes the angels because it must struggle against flesh to gain mastery over a nature angels do not possess.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: Novatians forbade remarriage. According to Novatian, woman was brought forth from man that she can know no other except him; and woman is given back to man so that, when what had been taken out of him is restored to him, he may not seek for anything belonging to another.

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Novatians forbade remarriage. According to Novatian, woman was brought forth from man that she can know no other except him; and woman is given back to man so that, when what had been taken out of him is restored to him, he may not seek for anything belonging to another.

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Novatians held that it is virtuous to set down certain restrictions in marriage regarding continence.

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Novatians held that it is virtuous to set down certain restrictions in marriage regarding continence.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no explicit mention in fasting. However, Novatians held that we should choose only the things that improve our soul and, although in the Gospel the use of foods is granted to us in every respect, one must realize that the use of these foods is given to us, however, with the law of frugality and moderation. In this sense, this kind of choice could be considered as a mode of fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Novatian wrote an epistle discussing the prohibitions that the Jewish Law enforced on certain types of food. According to Novatian, Divine benevolence has provided human needs with adequate kinds of foods to suit every age. Hearty flesh meat is proffered to men who must now cultivate the entire world and not merely take care of paradise. Since the cultivation of the land requires so much exertion, the human body had to be sustained with something more substantial. It is evident that all these foods enjoy again the blessings they received at their creation, now that the Law has ended, and that Christians must not return to the legal prohibition of foods commanded for certain reasons, and which evangelical liberty, setting Christians free from its bondage, has now discontinued. However, Novatian holds that Christians should not partake of what has been offered to idols. Although with regard to God's creation every food is clean, once it has been offered to demons, it is defiled for God, insofar as it is offered to idols. When this is taken as food, it nourishes the one who partakes of it for the devil, not for God, and makes him a table-companion of an idol, not of Christ.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Novatian's followers deliberately separated themselves and their communities from other Christian communities and called themselves "Catharoi" or "Purists" to reflect their desire not to be identified with what they regarded as the lax and tolerant practices of a corrupt ecclesiastical power.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Novatians had always a successor of Novatian in Rome and they were governed by their own bishops.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

– No

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: However, in Paphlagonia, soldiers that were sent by the Emperor Constantius to enforce conformity with the semi-Arian doctrine were attacked and slew by Novatian peasants.

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

- No
- No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

- No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

- Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- No

Notes: Not punishment exactly, however persecutions. Constantine the Great was the first to consider Novatians as schismatics, not heretics, closed their churches and their cemeteries. They were persecuted by the emperor Constantius. The Arian emperor Valens persecuted them as well and Honorius included Novatians in a law against heretics in 412.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Field doesn't know
- Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Novatians had always a successor of Novatian in Rome and they were governed by their own bishops.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

- No
- No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Field doesn't know
- Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

- No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

- No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

- No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

- Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Not punishment exactly, however persecutions. Constantine the Great was the first to consider Novatians as schismatics, not heretics, closed their churches and their cemeteries. They were persecuted by the emperor Constantius. The Arian emperor Valens persecuted them as well and Honorius included Novatians in a law against heretics in 412.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: However, in Paphlagonia, soldiers that were sent by the Emperor Constantius to enforce conformity with the semi-Arian doctrine were attacked and slew by Novatian peasants.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

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